

Abstract

This study attempts to show that J.M Coetzee's novel *Waiting for the Barbarians* hampers the construction of binary opposition which others the natives by presenting them as *barbarians* or *savage*. By peeling each layer of this book, this study will focus, empires purpose of this type of 'Othering' and the mechanisms used by them to manipulate the language and framework of history. The established binary constructs a view of the Colonials as civilized, rational, and good; On the other hand, it presents the aboriginals as primitive, irrational, and bad. Postcolonial novels and colonial reality show that the so-called civilized society is converted over time and carries a masked identity. Coetzee's questioned the imperial notion to label the natives as barbarian without mentioning the setting time and place. This study challenges the racist concept of *barbarian* by seeing the novel through postcolonial and psychoanalytic theories' prisms.

Introduction:

The South African white writer J. M. Coetzee made a decent impression on contemporary literature, despite the critics claim that he uses apartheid for fame. In addition to many other awards, it is fair to assume that Coetzee's novels made an unbelievable contribution to world literature, two times as the Booker Prize recipient, 1983 and 1998; and maybe the most coveted honor of all, the Nobel Prize for literature 2003. The works of Coetzee are typically not lengthy, so each word gets more central.

Published in 1980, Coetzee's third novel *Waiting for the Barbarians*, was the book that brought him international acclaim. Coetzee's title is drawn from the poem of the same name by the Greek poet C.P. Cavafy (1863-1933). Cavafy's poem presents the Roman Empire, decadent, precarious, awaiting the arrival of 'the barbarians' who will take over government machinery. This 'waiting' is an anticipation of the imperialist self-prophecy, a form of justification that is also self-negation: the imperialist project is based on the perception of the barbarian other and the anticipation of the eventual succession of this 'other'. In the poem, the barbarians fail to arrive – they cease to exist – and no longer embody 'a kind of solution'. Cavafy's poem identifies the contradictory dependence on the other that underpins Imperialism. While Colonel Joll is waiting for the *barbarian other*, the Magistrate has been waiting for a different barbarism manifestation. Colonel Joll, like the Romans in Cavafy's poem, needs to discover barbarians to validate his mission and the existence of the Empire.

In this study, the notion of *barbarian* will be analyzed through Edward Said's theory of 'Barbarians' from the book *Culture and Imperialism* (1993). Various theories of Homi k. Bhabha, Gayatri Spivak and Ania Loomba will be used to address the colonial tendency of 'Othering'. Jacques Lacan's psychoanalytic notion of the 'gaze' and Jeremy Bentham's idea of the 'Panopticon' will be used to show how the colonized are seen by the Empire.

The residents of the colonial settlements live in constant fear of being invaded. Lights will be shade on who are really the invaders. The colonial justification of torture and violence will severely be questioned to reveal the so-called civilized Empire's mask.

Some J.M Coetzee's essays are brought to show the writers' view regarding the Empire's attitude. The role of language in the novel will also be analyzed to indicate how language is manipulated to

create a one-sided framework of history. Finally, light will be shed on the Magistrates desire to choose a different path to show that his rebellion is futile

Review of the Literature:

Colonialism is a process during which dominant groups employ their supreme power and domination over the colonized people through exploitation, degradation, and torture. For the sake of constructing a national unity and consciousness, white colonial identity and imperial powers exploited and violated the Colonized people economically and culturally. Concerning racist problems, race ideology was also a crucial part of the construction and naturalization of an unequal form of intercultural relations. Together with political and economic propagandas, literary representations also played an essential role in constructing imperialistic behaviors and colonial powers' ideas.

Historians initially used the word 'postcolonial' to describe the time following colonization. Literary criticism has been used since the late 1970s to address the various cultural, political, and linguistic consequences of colonialism. Postcolonialism has subsequently been commonly used as a term for the political, linguistic and cultural history of societies that were former European colonies" (Ashcroft et al., 2000: 186).

Whether one calls it postcolonial or postcolonialism, the postcoloniality theory is as diverse and complex as the countries it has affected. In this paper, the author will use the term postcolonial to refer to the postcolonial theory and the term postcolonial when referring to a country liberated from colonialism. Postcolonial literature and theory manifest themselves differently from country to country, but the postcolonial experience itself ensures that they have some aspects in common. Ania Loomba stresses that "if it is uprooted from specific locations, 'postcoloniality' cannot be meaningfully investigated" (1998, 19); thus, it is essential when studying postcolonial literature to make distinctions according to place. In John McLeod's terms, an important distinction is between colonialism and postcolonialism (2000, 32). Colonialism includes, amongst other things, the internalization of certain forms of representation through language. It is not given that these internalizations magically disappear when a country becomes independent: "Colonialism's

representation, reading practices, and values are not so easily dislodged" (ibid.). McLeod goes on to say that postcoloniality is achieved by challenging the assumptions imposed by colonialism. In literature, the "given" truth is questioned in multiple ways: the idea of the "empire writes back" is one of the many examples found in Coetzee's *Foe*. Another is rewriting the myths imposed by the oppressors, visible in *In the Heart of the Country*. As has already been established, Coetzee questions "truth" and meaning in his novels as well as in his articles and essays. In *Waiting for the Barbarians*, Coetzee investigates the silence of torture and its victims and examines the language of authority, which in this novel does not quite correspond with an "objective" perception of the truth. The myth of the empty land in South Africa was central to justifying the Afrikaners' right to the land, which led to the 'Other' silencing. Coetzee deals with the silent 'Other' in many of his works, almost literally so in *Foe*, where the black Friday has had his tongue cut out. Coetzee's works are then central to writing back or rewriting in postcolonial South Africa. As is visible, reading and writing are essential parts of both imposing colonial values onto someone else and freeing oneself from them and finding a new identity.

Ania Loomba points out how the term 'colonial' wipes out the history of a place before colonization (17). Loomba shows how the term itself, as defined in the OED, illustrates this, being described as a settlement in the new country that maintains bonds to the parent state. What is significant, however, is how "[t]his definition, quite remarkably, avoids any reference to people other than the colonizers, people who might already have been living in those places where colonies were established. Hence it evacuates the word 'colonialism' of any implication of an encounter between peoples, or conquest and domination" (1-2). Thus, we find that the term itself participates in the "colonial" act of silencing the 'Other'. The colonial mission has in no small extent silenced or given a new voice to the 'Other', a voice which to begin with has not been theirs, and whose aim it has been to impose a set identity unto the 'Other'. This often comes in terms of binary oppositions, where the other's identity is the negative opposite of colonial masters. A myth that justifies the exploitation of the oppressed is created. According to John McLeod, colonial writing of the Other relates to representation and interpellation: "Colonialism, then, is an operation of discourse, and as an operation of discourse it interpolates colonial subjects by incorporating them in a system of representation./'interpellation' means 'calling'; the idea is that ideology calls us, and we turn and recognize who we are" (37). As the writer of this paper mentioned above, in the encounter between the Colonizer and the 'Other,' myths are created. The Colonizers write the myth of the 'Other,' and

Coetzee points out an example of this in *White Writing*, showing how the writing of the 'Hottentot' as amongst other things lazy and idle contributes to creating Othering and racism. By European standards, Coetzee says, being idle was considered ungodly (20), and here we find the entrance of ideology. Because the Europeans brought with them an ideology of hard work and labor, the natives fell short of this paradigm. This ultimately set them apart as embodying a vice that could infect the Europeans if they did not maintain their superiority. An important part of creating a myth of the 'Other's was to ensure a separate unitary identification for the Colonizers' vis -á -vis the Colonized.

Theoretical Framework:

The simple boundary between the Empire and the Barbarians, the civilized and uncivilized space, rests on colonial ideology. The law of reason and civility extends in this worldview until the farthest outpost of the Empire, where the guardians of reason wage their relentless struggle from the watchtowers to separate the delicate domain of humanity from its barbaric others. To establish the relationship of domination, the binary logic of Imperialism is essential, accommodating "such fundamental binary impulses within imperialism as the impulse to exploit and the impulse to civilize" (Ashcroft et al 1998, 24).

Ethnic theorists have often dwelled on the antithetical nature of ethnicity. In ethnic name-calling the tendency persists, as George Murdock argued in Seligman's *Encyclopaedia of the Social Sciences*, that a people usually calls itself either by a flattering name or by a term signifying simply 'men', 'men of men', 'first men', or 'people'. Aliens on the other hand, are regarded as something less than men; they are styled 'barbarians' or are known by some derogatory term corresponding to such modern American ethnic tags as 'bohunk', 'chink', 'dago', 'frog', 'greaser', 'nigger', 'sheeny' and 'wop'.
(Murdock 1931:613)

As Agnes Heller writes, what 'is now called "ethnocentrism" is the natural attitude of all cultures toward alien ones' (Heller 1984:271).

In one of the most influential postcolonial theory works, *Orientalism*, Edward Said has shown how systematic discourse is conducted. The development of the homogeneous picture of the racially inferior Orient as the European "absolute other" has been instrumental for the legitimization of the imperial conquest and the constitution of the West's supremacy and authority.

"The "Oriental" was created by the nexus of power and knowledge and in a way obliterated him as a human being." (Said 2006, 27).

The discursive opposition between the Colonizer and the colonized is unsettled by ambivalence at the center of colonial discourse and disrupts the assumptions of colonial dominance. Therefore, a big paradox of the colonial relationship is that "it produces the seed of its own destruction" (Ashcroft et al 1998, 13). Lacan's psychoanalytic notion of the gaze was essential to the dialectical phase of distinction between the Colonizer and the colonized in postcolonial discourse. After Lacan, Ashcroft, Griffiths and Tiffin note that "the other is important to the subject because in its gaze the subject exists"(1998, 170). However, the gaze does not emanate exclusively from the subject that settles on the object and constitutes it. Instead, it is a link between the spectator and the subject viewed.

Foucault's many works are based on the relationship between power and knowledge. Power produces knowledge, as in how society confines people who have gone mad. This confinement creates new kinds of sciences about those confined, which furthers the power cycle over them. Foucault's main focus in *Madness and Civilization* is language. This paper also attempts to show the underlying politics of discourse the Empire practices. Foucault, in his book *Discipline and Punish*, seeks to analyze punishment in its social context and to examine how changing power relations affected punishment. He begins by analyzing the situation before the eighteenth century when public execution and corporal punishment were essential punishments. The eighteenth-century saw various calls for reform of punishment, but reformers were not motivated by a concern for prisoners' welfare, he says. They wanted to make power operate more efficiently, according to Foucault. The penitentiary is the next development. It combines the prison with the workshop and the hospital. It replaces the prisoner with the delinquent in order to marginalize and control prevalent behavior, he writes. It aims both to deprive the individual of his freedom and to reform

him, he adds. Criticism of the failure of prisons misses the point because failure is part of its very nature.

The aim of prison and the carceral system is to produce delinquency as a means of structuring and controlling crime. Calls for its abolition fail to recognize the depth at which it is embedded in modern society. Foucault also details how punishment took the form of public torture so that members of society could witness the absolute power of the sovereign and therein learn to obey because crimes were committed against the sovereign. In the novel, both the Magistrate and the Barbarians were sentenced to public humiliation and torture; according to Foucault, this type of act is an authoritarian tendency to display hegemony. To explain disciplinary power, Foucault famously employs Jeremy Bentham's notion of the Panopticon. The architectural layout of a prison where the guards reside within a central tower and maintain surveillance over all inmates is a form of power. For Foucault, 'the major effect of the Panopticon [was] to induce in the inmate a state of conscious and permanent visibility.'

Gayatri Spivak introduces the word 'othering' to account for the mechanism by which 'other' subjects are created by imperial discourse. This is a dialectical process because at the same time as its colonized, others are produced as subjects, "the colonizing Other is created"(Ashcroft, et al 1998, 171).

As Ania Loomba says, the process of Othering as the construction of the culturally and racially inferior subjects is driven by what Abdul JanMohamed called the 'Manichean allegory' that generates a binary opposition between races (Loomba 1998, 105). Besides, stereotypical images of the other feed on the power/knowledge that fixes the identities of the two opposed entities, since it is on the picture of the dark barbarian other that the Eurocentric cultures have developed their own fragile sense of society and identity (Hamadeh 2005). Robert Young explains that one of the key contributions of Bhabha to the field was to supplement Said's Foucauldian study of the discursive development of the Orient, in that he develops the implications of Said's idea that there is a distinction between a "manifest" and a "latent" Orientalism, "the conscious body of Oriental scientific knowledge"(Young 1995, 153).

Thus both the Colonizer and the colonized are under ideology's sway, responding and gaining identity and a sense of self through its call. The individual is rendered powerless against ideology. However, there is also a certain sense of assent and dissent involved. If we consider Loomba's

argument, Gramsci's theory of hegemony also has its place in the issues of imposed identity: "Hegemony is power achieved through a combination of coercion and consent"; one gains power over someone through "creating subjects who 'willingly' submit to being ruled" (29). This is connected through ideology in the following way: "Ideology is crucial in creating consent; it is the medium through which certain ideas are transmitted, and more importantly, held to be true." (ibid.). Thus yet again, ideology comes to the aid of the Colonizer and the possessors of power.

Colonial Gaze can be defined as how the colonial agenda seeks to maintain and legitimate power by determining colonial realities, including the dehumanization of colonial subjects and the perpetual separation of Us (colonizers, civilized) and Other (colonized, savage). In postcolonial discourse, Lacan's psychoanalytic notion of the gaze has been crucial for the dialectical process of identification between the Colonizer and the colonized. The act of being-looked-at Sartre calls the "alienation of myself" involving the "Alienation of the world which I organize" In the colonial context, the gaze is understood as a state of anxiety and displacement. The colonizer experiences once he realizes that the object of his colonial gaze is gazing back at him.

Good fences make good neighbors:

This section's title is taken from Robert Frost's 1914 poem 'Mending Wall' to show how the Empire constructs invisible fences literally and philosophically to 'other' the aboriginals. According to Webster's new universal unabridged dictionary (1972)

"A Barbarian is a human who is perceived to be uncivilized. In idiomatic or figurative usage, a 'barbarian' may also be an individual reference to a brutal, cruel, warlike, and insensitive, or **insane** person. "

The word 'insane' is important here since the discussion attempts to reveal who snows madness. In order to discuss this matter, Michel Foucault's 1965 book, *Madness and Civilization* will be used. Edward said comments about the notion of 'Barbarians' in *culture and Imperialism*. According to him, colonizers have been affected by the 'mysterious East.' Since the discoveries started. They claim that they brought civilization to the primitive or barbaric people; but when they misbehave or become rebellious, imperial powers think that barbaric people deserve to be ruled (Said, 1994:1)

Throughout the novel, Coetzee reveals the colonizers' attempt to construct boundaries or fences between the so-called civil society and the aboriginals. The fences between the rational and insane others are most accurately presented waiting for the Barbarians. Many critics have opined the novel is a political allegory of the South African apartheid-era, but the author will not focus on that. Instead the focus will be given to the binary oppositions found in the text.

These binary oppositions are often closely connected, and their vagueness is demonstrated in the novel. Influenced by these oppositions, the Magistrate questions his own identity. The Magistrate is the narrator of the story who is the administrator of a settler outpost of an indeterminate place and time and which thus creates a kind of temporal no-mans-land or 'interregnum.' Gordimer coopted this term from the Italian Marxist, Antonio Gramsci's reinterpretation, which denotes a transitional period between regimes when in Gramsci's words,

"The old is dying, and the new cannot be born" (Nadine Gordimer, *Essential Gesture* 263)

The isolated setting at a marginal outpost place it directly into the postcolonial discourse of power, of constructing nation, of Othering, and of belonging and non-belonging. Homi Bhabha talks about the national construct in "Dissemination: Time, narrative and the margins of the modern nation," in *The Location of Culture* (pp.139-170). In the course of his argument, Bhabha questions who can write or represent a nation when the nation's heterogeneity leads to a split in the 'narrative authority.' However, a uniting factor is to join in common hatred. Quoting Freud, Bhabha states

"It is always possible to bind together a considerable number of people in love, so long as there are other people left to receive the manifestation of their aggressiveness." (149)

Similarly, in the novel, the townspeople accepted the stranger fisher folks as long as they are considered enemies of the 'barbarians.' Gallagher asserts, the nation "achieves strength, unity and identity" by creating the notions of the 'other,' the enemy at the gate (1991, 132), and this is what the emissaries of Empire, in the guise of Joll and Mandel, seek to gain.

According to Ania Loomba, the 'other's' creation depends on binary oppositions and is crucial not only for creating images of the outsider but equally essential for constructing the insider, the (usually white European male) self (1998,104). The Empire presents two views of colonial rule; both are necessary for the success of the Empire. The Magistrate demonstrates a conservative view of the imperial rule where the relationship with the natives only maintained for trading purposes,

whereas Joll and Mandel represent a more radical view of Colonizer's demonstration of power before its subjects.

In one part of the novel, the soldiers, having invaded the fisher folk's living area, trigger a motion where the fisherfolk, in turn, are forced to invade the town. It is evident from this that the townspeople perceive the fisherfolk as savages, but not 'barbarians.'

"There has been a drift of refugees to the town, fisherfolk from the tiny settlements dotted along the river and the northern lakeshore, speaking a language no one understands, carrying their households on their backs, with their gaunt dogs and rickety children trailing behind them. People crowded around them when they first came. "Was it the barbarians who chased you out?" they asked, making fierce faces, stretching imaginary bows. No one asked about the imperial soldiery or the brush-fires they set." (Coetzee 136)

Whereas the townspeople consider them victims of the 'barbarian' attack, the Magistrate opposes that the Empire has driven the fisherfolk out of their homes. Once they started getting too comfortable, the townspeople no longer see them as allies against a common enemy and are pushed outside the settlements. The soldiers, on the other hand, get away with their crimes and invasions because they are protecting the border, keeping the settlement safe from the 'barbarians.'

Half Devil and Half Child:

This title is borrowed from Rudyard Kipling's poem "The White Man's Burden (1899)" Kipling used these words to address the 'inferior' non-Europeans. This line shows the biased discourse the people in power create to manipulate language and history. Language plays a vital role in this novel. The agents of Empire possess a different perception of language. For example, colonel Joll explains to the Magistrate how, in the torture chamber, "a certain tone enters the voice of a man who is feeling the truth" (Coetzee, p.5). Initially, the Magistrate assumes Joll must have an ear that is remarkably sensitive to linguistic inflection. However, his main aim is to summarize all inflection to the single tone of pain, which is only true to him, in the same way, the Colonizer always tends to destroy indigenous culture, including indigenous language. At one point, indigenous language is taken as a sign of guilt; some of Joll's first prisoners turn out to be fisherfolk rather than 'barbarians.' The soldiers arrested them because they could not understand their

language. For the colonizers,' otherness denoted by language is a threat that must be neutralized. (Coetzee, 18)

Through the language, the relationship between various characters is cleanly implicated, especially the relationship between the Magistrate and the barbarian girl. When the Magistrate returned the girl to her family, he heard the girl talking fluently in the pidgin language. He realized that she is ' a witty, attractive, young woman,' and he regrets not having asked her to teach him this language (Coetzee, 63). The Empire even changes Magistrate's identity when the Magistrate did not conform to the imperial agents' aims. When the Magistrate returns to town after handing the girl over to her family. Empire charges him for "consorting with the enemy" and starts to treat their agent as 'other.' Colonel Joll tells the Magistrate,

"to people in this town, you are not the one just man; you are simply a clown, a madman. You are dirty, you stink, they can smell you a mile away". (Coetzee 124)

After this, Mandel, with help from the mob, makes the Magistrate become the clown and madman Joll suggested. The Magistrate accepts his situation when he realizes he does not have the power to write history. It is the people like Mandel and Joll who can rewrite history. When Magistrate asks officer Mandel if he is still a prisoner or not, Mandel shows him Empire's power over context by saying.

"How can you be a prisoner when we have no record of you? Do you think we do not keep records? We have no record of you, so you must be a free man". (Coetzee 176)

The novel's related idea is revealed in those episodes featuring the wooden slips bearing an ancient script. The Magistrate found them near an excavation site and kept himself busy deciphering meaning from it. Nevertheless, Joll is determined to establish his meaning behind the slips. By establishing a singular meaning behind the aboriginal craftworks, Joll is attempting to eradicate African prehistory because this prehistory may shake colonial invader's ideology. At the end of the novel, the Magistrate sets about writing a history of his experience but dismisses his version of history as incomplete. Finally, he recognizes perhaps he cannot tell the whole story of Empire. Thus Coetzee attempts to introduce the idea of an alternative framework for history, an alternative form of narrative, even though the Magistrate does not seem well placed to realize such a narrative.

Two little discs of glass:

This line appears in the very first paragraph of *Waiting for the Barbarians*. The line is about Colonel Joll's sunglasses, who possesses a blurred view of the world. He believes that "Pain is truth; all else is subject to doubt." It is Joll who inflicts pain on both the barbarian girls' family and the Magistrate. That is why outlook toward pain and justification of torture should be questioned.

Colonel Joll is a figure, masked behind the sunglasses. He has modified his sight and "protected from the metaphor of landscape" (Bhabha 295). As a result, his perception of the border outpost on the fringes of the desert remains the same as in the capital city, the metropolis for which he stands. Wherever he goes, he remains within the Empire, and the truth he seeks can only be the truth of the Empire. Joll's this type of activities can be related to what Elleke Boehmer calls the 'Colonial Gaze.' According to Boehmer: "The gaze was manifest in activities of investigation, examination, inspection poring over, which were accompaniments to the colonial penetration of a country." (Boehmer 81)

Colonel Joll's Shade and his tendency to look at everything through these glasses can be related to Foucault's theory of the Panopticon. According to Michel Foucault, the Panopticon "is a machine for dissociating the see/being seen dyad: in the peripheral ring, one sees everything without ever being seen" (Foucault, 202). It originally referred to a construct with cells surrounding a tower. From the tower, one can have a complete view of the cells and the inmates of the cells. On the other hand, the inmates could not see into the tower and could never be sure they were not being watched.

The same detachment from seeing and being not seen can be found in Colonel Joll's shades. Because his eyes are prevented from the scorching heat of the sun, he can see 'everything', and the black discs prevent his eyes from being seen. The idea of the Panopticon is significant because it says who has the authority to watch, and it represents the initialization of authority and power. The Magistrate's constant fear of being watched by Joll and Mandel represents the existence of the Panopticon in the novel. The Magistrate says after escaping from prison, "it is only a matter of time before I am discovered.... I used to think they are sitting in another room discussing me". Moreover, the novels setting with watchtowers and barbed walls consisting of prison with inmates in the center is quite similar to Foucault's notion of the Panopticon.

John Maxwell Coetzee, in his 1986 essay, "Into the Dark Chamber: The writer and the South African state," Coetzee describes *Waiting for Barbarians* as a novel about torture and the impact of torture on the 'man of conscience.' Joll tortures the older man of the native people so brutally that "his grey beard is caked with blood." The intensity of torture on the barbarian girl makes her blind. The torture endured by the Magistrate includes a public beating, being forced to drink pints of brine, and a mock hanging that nearly strangles him. Butler writes that,

"Violence in the name of civilization reveals its own barbarism even as it 'justifies' its own violence by presuming the barbaric sub-humanity of the 'other' against whom that violence is waged." (93)

The gory picture that Coetzee paints before us demonstrates that violence is intensified because of racial differences in the novel. After delivering the girl back to the Barbarian tribe, the Magistrate returns to his town and is immediately imprisoned by Joll for 'consorting with the enemy.' In what could be the most brutal representation of physical violence in the entire novel, the Magistrate witnesses the collective beating of a group of captured natives by the armed forces. The narrator, though technically attempting to escape, finds he cannot move away from the spectacle before him. He describes that,

"The Colonel steps forward, stooping over each prisoner in turn he rubs a handful of dust into his naked back and writes a word with a stick of charcoal. I read the words upside down: ENEMY. . . ENEMY. . . ENEMY. . . ENEMY. . . He steps back and folds his hands. At a distance of no more than twenty paces, he and I contemplate each other. Then the beating begins. The soldiers use the stout green cane staves, bringing them down with the heavy slapping sounds of washing-paddles, raising red welts on the prisoners' backs and buttocks. The black charcoal and ochre dust begin to run with sweat and blood. The game, I see, is to beat them till their backs are washed clean." (Coetzee 121)

The violent scene takes place in a town supposedly attached to a 'civilized' Empire, which can form its identity as such in opposition to the savagery of the barbarians. In this scene, even a little girl participates in beating the aboriginal. The 'civilized' town's people voluntarily took part in beating in such a number that there was a "scramble for the canes."

Joll and Mandel believe pressure, pain, and isolation lead to guilt's admittance to the so-called truth. However, the truth Joll finds is the one he has already set his mind to hear; the only truth he

will accept is that of guilt. The Magistrate recognized this and advised the barbarian boy under interrogation,

"Listen, you must tell the officer the truth. That is all he wants to hear from you---the truth".

Patrick Lenta's article "Legal Illegality: *Waiting for the Barbarians* after September 11" argues that the truth Joll is looking for is one that is required to be true by the Empire.

"Prolonged torture forces victims to try to comprehend the torturer's interest and present themselves in a way that is most likely to satisfy their torturers. After a time, the victim will say what the torturer wants to hear". (2006.75)

Later in the novel Coetzee himself proves Lenta's comment as truth, where the Magistrate tastes torture himself, he tells us: "I discover with surprise that after a little rest, after the application of a little pain, I can be made to move, to jump or skip or crawl or run a little further".(Coetzee 192)

The writer of the novel wants to show by making the barbarian girl disfigured and semi-blinded, the Empire transforms normal into abnormal. The Magistrate washes the girl's body to wash away the traces of the torture but in the end, it becomes apparent the scar will never go. In other words, Coetzee wants to indicate the Empire's crime against humanity cannot be forgotten or forgiven.

The Road Not Taken:

The final section of the essay is borrowed from Robert Frost's 1976 poem. This title is taken because after experiencing Empires gruesome torture, the Magistrate does not want to follow the path of madness that Joll and Mandel follow; besides, it will be shown who takes barbaric path of madness and who does not. Coetzee's novel's power lies in part in the Magistrates' realization that the boundaries between himself and the dehumanizing regime of Empire and the warped nations of the reason it promotes are disturbingly opaque. The Magistrates' position as both an oppressor and oppressed is experienced as a double consciousness that can only lead to madness. Michel

Foucault, in his 1965 book, *Madness and Civilization*, deals with the notion of 'madness' and 'civilization.' Foucault says,

"We have yet to write the history of that other form of madness. By which men, in the act of sovereign reason, confine their neighbors and communicate and recognize each other through the merciless language of non-madness". (Foucault ix)

Foucault is not giving us a medical definition of madness, which is connected to mental illness. He defines how the Europeans naturalize madness as a method of control. Society's need for self-definition boundaries necessitates constructing "The insane" as others, but this process is inherently self-revealing. In Coetzee's novel, the binaries of reason/unreason and mad/not-mad are exposed in the context of enlightenment thinking that serves to maintain the Empire's power.

In this novel, it is the Magistrate who decides not to take the colonizers path. The Magistrate is an archaeologist, an archivist, and a reader of texts and critics of Empire. He collected some poplar slips bearing strange inscriptions and struggles to prepare a record of the town. A central problem arises when the Magistrate tries to read the girl like a text. He says, "Until the marks on the girl's body are deciphered and understood, I cannot let go of her." (Coetzee 83) Thus, the Magistrate cannot come out of his colonial cocoon by seeing the girl as a 'blank page' and 'incomplete', he shows the colonial tendency of robbing the subjects of their identity.

A cynical critic of Empire, the Magistrate even questions the colonizers' act of reading. When he tries to decipher the poplar slips for Joll, he says, "Together they can be read as a domestic journal, or they can be read as a plan of war, or they can be turned on their sides and read as a history of the last years of the Empire—the old Empire, I mean" (Coetzee 158). Not only does this act of reading allow the Magistrate to launch a covert attack on Joll, but it also calls into question the Manichean allegory employed by the Empire to police its authority. By providing alternative readings and alluding to the barbarians' slips, the Magistrate satirizes Imperial colonial history's monolith, suggesting that truth is far more malleable than such histories would allow. By satirizing Joll and parodying the process by which Empire knows its subjects, the Magistrate exposes the truths of Empire and simultaneously calls into question over-determined representation practices of the Empire.

Madness lacks self-knowledge; thus the Magistrates' desire for the Barbarian girl should also be read as madness, given it is based on lack of reciprocity, self-interest and irrational negligence of truth justified through the magistrates' wavering belief in his altruistic motivation for taking her in. Jan Mohamed referred to the Magistrates' attitude toward the girl as fetishistic. According to him, the Magistrate shows a desire to be recognized by the other to clarify one's sense of self. The Magistrates' sexual pursuit toward the injured Barbarian girl can also be termed as his self-interest.

Arrested by Joll for supposedly "treasonably consorting with the enemy," dressed in a woman's frock and gibbeted on a tree, the Magistrate is diminished to what Mandel, Joll's henchman, calls a "clown a madman." Mandel scapegoats the Magistrate by reconstructing him as 'Other' and, thus, insane. Finally, Mandel and his men let the Magistrate roam freely like a half-mad and beggar.

The portrayal of the Magistrate by Mandel as insane corresponds with Foucault's thesis in *Discipline and Punish*: of the birth of the criminal subject during the Enlightenment. As Foucault writes, "From being an art of unbearable sensations, punishment has become an economy of suspended rights" (Discipline 11). Modern penal methods, such as Jeremy Bentham's Panopticon, shifted the object of punishment from the physical body to the soul, the self-regulation and consciousness-raising of the prisoner who kept alive, is allowed to experience guilt, remorse and to reform. The Magistrate declares that Mandel "deals with my soul" (Coetzee 129). Of course, in terms of the Barbarians, both the soul and the physical body are disciplined.

The madness of civilization is depicted in the torture events in the novel. When the Barbarian prisoners were beaten mercilessly under the watchful eye of Joll, the morally sickened Magistrate inverts the object of Joll's vile game from prisoner to Joll himself. Courageously putting his freedom in jeopardy in the name of justice, he rails,

"Those pitiable prisoners you brought in—are they the enemy I must fear? Is that what you say? You are the enemy, Colonel!" I can restrain myself no longer. I pound the desk with my fist. "You are the enemy, you have made the war, and you have given them all the martyrs they need—starting not now but a year ago when you committed your first filthy barbarities here! History will bear me out" (Coetzee 161)

Nevertheless, the text always returns us to the Magistrates' irrationality in his relationship with the girl and effectively turns a blind eye to the atrocities of Empire, including the murder of the old aboriginal man in the custody. The Magistrate does not want to take Joll and Mandel's path but unable to find a path of freedom also. In the end, he utters the sublime truth of the Empire. Empires henchmen, he says, are the "new Barbarians." The novel suggests that nurturing the fear of threat of the Barbarians is Empires' means of defining the "civilized" self. In this regard, Cavafy's poem can be quoted,

"And some who have just returned from the border say there are no barbarians any longer.

And now, what's going to happen to us without barbarians?

They were, those people, a kind of solution."

Constantine P. Cavafy, "Waiting for the Barbarians" (1904)

Conclusion: This paper has presented how Coetzee's novel *Waiting for the Barbarians* challenges the construction of binary opposition of civilized 'self' and the barbarian 'other.' In this process, diving into the colonials' mind, the mechanisms of apartheid are extracted. The racial tendency to establish superiority is also brought under criticism. One may argue that the redeemed Magistrate possesses an opportunity of an alternative ending through decolonizing the settlement. Nevertheless, in the novel, the Magistrate does not turn to violence; his eerie silence in many events and his treatment of the tortured native girl makes him an integral part of the oppressive group. We cannot say that he ultimately comes out of the colonial shell because at the end of the novel, he still believes that the natives will forget everything when they will taste modern inventions such as 'mulberry Jam.' Thus, the Magistrate and Colonel become two sides of the same Imperial coin.

Coetzee provides several borders in the novel to show a lack of comprehension from the colonizers' side. These borders also show how Manichean allegories are employed to cement the domination over the colonized people. In his essay "Into the Dark Chamber," Coetzee defined *Waiting for the*

Barbarians as a novel highlighting the impact of torture on a 'man of conscience.' This realization is experienced by the Magistrate when he experiences mock hanging by Mandel and the mob. The gory acts of tortures that Colonel Joll and his men took part in clearly show that the Empire and its agents are the real savages.

After the torture, the Magistrate returns from his rebellious attitude, but again he is the only character in the novel who has a sense of guilt who decides not to take the road of his people; thus, we can call him Coetzee's tortured 'man of conscience.' Because it is from the Magistrate's consciousness, the readers become aware of Imperial discursive power's mechanics. Coetzee's narration makes it clear that 'barbarians' in the novel exist only in colonizers' rumor and paranoia. In this way, J.M. Coetzee challenges the colonial definition of savage barbarians and suggest that Empire's henchman are the 'new Barbarians.' *Waiting for the Barbarians* implicates that nurturing the Barbarians' fear of threat is Empires' means of defining the civilized self and its lifeline to exist. Coetzee brings before the readers the reasons for the colonizers' tendency of creating 'Other.' He says,

"One thought alone preoccupies the submerged mind of Empire: how not to end, how not to die, how to prolong its era" (Coetzee 187)

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